

**A CORRELATION STUDY BETWEEN SELF-CONCEPT AND
LEADERSHIP AMONG PRIMARY TEACHER**

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Abstract :

The present research deals with Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher. The samples comprise 60 rural and urban Primary Teacher by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are Self-concept and Leadership Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The data was analyzed using r.

Findings

There is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.

Keywords: self-concept and Leadership

Introduction:

Self-concept is the image that we have of ourselves. How exactly does this self-image form and change over time? This image develops in a number of ways but is particularly influenced by our interactions with important people in our lives

The self-concept as an organizer of behavior is of great importance. Self-concept refers to the experience of one's own being. It includes what people come to know about themselves through experience, reflection and feedback from others. It is an organized cognitive structure comprised of a set of attitudes, beliefs, values, variety of habits, abilities, out looks, ideas and feelings of a person. Consistency of behavior and continuity of identity are two of the chief properties of the self-concept. Wylie 1974, Brook over 1988 and Mishap 1989 indicates that self-concept is positively related with their school achievement. Self-concept is a factor which helps to study the human behavior and personality

Leadership is a necessary part of the social process. Any group, association, organization or community functions the way its leader leads it. It is truer in the collectivistic cultures like India where people follow the path shown by the great people

Some characteristic of Leaders are a) adaptable of situations b) alert towards social situation c) cooperative d) decisive e) dependable f) assertive g) confident and persistent h) knowledge

Hence the investigators selected the topic Correlation between self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.

Statement of the Problem

"A Correlation study between Self-concept and Leadership among Primary Teacher."

Objective

1. To identify the correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.
2. To identify the correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of male Primary Teacher.
3. To identify the correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of female Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.
2. There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of female Primary Teacher.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study of the Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher .The sample comprise for the present study is 60 Primary Teacher. Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The following tools were used to collect the data from Primary Teacher. Self-concept and Leadership Questionnaire The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Hypotheses:

1. **There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.**

Primary Teacher	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Self-concept	60	58	.65	.250
	Leadership				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is .250 and the obtain 'r' value is .65 So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.

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Hypotheses:

2 There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of male Primary Teacher.

Male Primary Teacher.	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Self-concept	30	28	0.61	.361
	Leadership				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.61. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of male Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

3 There is no significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Female Primary Teacher.

Female Primary Teacher.	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Self-concept	30	28	0.63	.361
	Leadership				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.63. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of female Primary Teacher.

Findings

1. There is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher.
2. There is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of female Primary Teacher.

Conclusion

The findings of present study shows that the significant correlation between Self-concept and Leadership of Primary Teacher. Is observed in case male, female Primary Teacher.

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